

Defining what is learned – challenges in continuous learning and improvement

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Abstract

This paper is connected to a research project called Rezbuid (REfurbishment decision making platform through advanced technologies for near Zero energy BUILDing renovation). Rezbuid is a European Union project that aims to define a collaborative refurbishment ecosystem focused on the existing residential building stock.

This paper is based on a study that investigates the Rezbuid project in order to find out systematically and periodically the project partners' reflection on their experiences in the project so far. The experiences can include, among other things, best practices, lessons learned, challenges and opportunities. These findings can be translated into learning and then performance improvement. Hence, this paper embarks on the following research question: How to improve performance of a research project systematically by continuous learning? To answer this question, it is vital to define what we learn and what knowledge that we have actually gained. This paper aims to shed some light on certain vital aspects of making such definition. This is the major focus of this paper.

The primary way to capture learning in the project is carried out by the following manner: Rezbuid has regular meetings with all of its partners – twice a year (in addition to more frequent online meetings). These meetings are arenas for collective reflection, sharing knowledge and experience, identifying challenges and opportunities.

A questionnaire is used to capture lessons learned in a six month period between project-partner-meetings. The questionnaire too provides possibilities for reflection and hence contributes to learning. It deals with, for instance, the following issues:

- The degree of understanding that is obtained regarding own and other work-packages, as well as the project as whole
- Skills that contributed to the project and the challenges of the project during the period
- Improvement possibilities
- Most interesting result for the project partner and the corresponding organization, obtained during the period

Information obtained from the project partners will be analyzed and shared regularly, so that appropriate actions can be devised to improve performance of the project.

Keywords: Reflection, Conversation, Dialog, Sense making, Ba, Building refurbishment

1. Introduction

Research projects are aimed at adding value to the society. Conducting research projects effectively, influences results of research projects. Thus, it is important to look for and utilize opportunities for improving project performance. Learning is one of the notions to consider in this regard. This paper will look at a learning process in a research project that is taken place at different time periods during the project's execution. This is

a conceptual paper. However, some relevant moments / instances of the research projects will be presented in order to illustrate the nature of the learning process.

The project that this paper focuses on, is called "REZBUILD" (REfurbishment decision making platform through advanced technologies for near Zero energy BUILDing renovation)". The REZBUILD project grows with the main aim of defining a collaborative refurbishment ecosystem focused on the existing residential building stock. The project was awarded by the European Commission with a H2020 Programme Grant of € 6,996,128.25. Total budget is € 9,038,208.75. REZBUILD is a 4-year project that was started in October 2017. The project will base its refurbishment ecosystem on the integration of cost-effective technologies, business models and life-cycles interaction. The project will focus on the retrofit of diverse residential typologies, interconnecting every building renovation stage as well as all stakeholders. For more information of the project, see <https://rezbuildproject.eu/>.

2. Projects as learning arenas

Projects are per definition unique. This means that there is something new that will be applied and / or produced in projects, for example, new products, tools, work-process, etc. In addition, new experiences will be gained in projects by, for example, dealing with new challenges and collaborating with new partners. These experiences provide opportunities for understanding complex situations better, and therefore strengthen the ability to handle new challenges better in the future. Hence, the unique nature of projects presents an arena for creating new knowledge.

Though projects are per definition unique, there are certain known elements that are applied in projects. Known solutions – in the form of, for example, tools, methods and processes – are often applied in projects. These known solutions are applied either directly or with modifications according to the context in which they are going to be applied. Known solutions can also be formed in a new combination to address a need or a problem. Hence, projects also present an arena for sharing knowledge.

The two paragraphs mentioned above point out a pivotal aspect of learning: Knowledge ambidexterity, which includes both knowledge exploration and knowledge exploitation. Knowledge ambidexterity plays an important role in learning processes in projects. Learning is an important and integral part of improving performance in projects. R&D projects are not exceptional.

In this paper, we will describe how knowledge sharing and knowledge creation take place in the Rezbuild project. The primary aim of learning and knowledge sharing is to improve the project's performance.

3. Knowledge and learning

We consider the following three descriptions of knowledge in connection with this paper:

As the first description, we consider a categorization presented by Spender (2008) that looks at knowledge in three major categories:

- Knowledge-as-data: The category tends to suggest that knowledge is considered as an object, and to point out the explicit and objective characteristics of knowledge
- Knowledge-as-meaning: This category deals with reflection and sense-making
- Knowledge-as-practice: This category views knowledge beyond the cognitive spectrum – beyond the sense-making aspect. It incorporates tacit characteristics of knowledge

As the second description, we consider the following definition, given by Davenport and Prusak (1998, page 5):

"Knowledge is a fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information and expert insight that provides a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information. It originates and is applied in the minds of knowers. In organizations, it often becomes embedded not only in documents or repositories but also in organizational routines, processes, practices and norms".

In our opinion, the above definition reflects and summarizes the categorization given by Spender (2008).

Thirdly, we consider the description of knowledge that is presented by Stacey. Stacey looks at knowledge creation in organizations from the perspective of complex responsive processes of relating. According to Stacey, knowledge is continuously reproduced and potentially transformed during interaction between people (2001-a). How people communicate and respond to each other plays a key role in creating knowledge.

In his book "Complex responsive processes in Organizations – Learning and knowledge creation" (2001-b, page 189), Stacey says:

"From this perspective, knowledge is meaning and it can only emerge in the communicative interaction between people. It emerges as meaning in the ongoing relating between people in the living present. This is an evolutionary concept of knowledge as meaning continuously reproduced and potentially transformed in action. Knowledge is, therefore, the thematic patterns organizing the experience of being together."

The above description can also be considered, at least to a certain degree, in connection with Lave & Wenger. According to Lave & Wenger (1991), learning is a social process in which an individual engages in negotiations and re-negotiations with others to acquire his/her knowledge. Knowledge is hence a co-constructed social process.

In an organizational world that characterizes high degree of complexity, it may not be always possible to easily identify what causes what, how it causes, why it causes, who causes, when it causes, where it causes. This situation has implications for learning and for defining what knowledge that we gained through the learning process.

Complexity that prevails in organizations directs us to look critically at the concept of learning and knowledge sharing. The critical view could tell us that knowledge is not merely an object; knowledge is not just data. Knowledge is about creating meaning through discussion and reflection – through which the non-linear nature of causal connections can be explored, understood and dealt with. In other words, knowledge "resides" in relationships and emerges through conversation and collective reflection. This knowledge is further developed when it is applied and followed by reflecting on and dealing with the results of the application. The above description also points out the connection between two dimensions of knowledge: cognitive development and behavioural development. (For more on these two dimensions, please refer Fiol & Lyles (1985).)

4. Reflection and sense making

Forming and strengthening relationships among cooperating organizational members encompass, among other things, individual and collective reflection on actions and outcomes that they experience in their work settings. When reflection is considered in connection with a professional action that an organizational member participates, then it can be viewed as reflection-on-action and reflection-in-action (Schön, 1998). Reflection-on-action is a process in which the individual reflects on his or her past experience or on a future act deliberately or unintentionally. Reflection-in-action is a process in which the individual reflects on what he or she is experiencing while he or she is engaging in the activity. These two categories of reflection play a notable role in the learning process. A combination of self-reflection and collective reflection can uncover – through dialog – possible non-linear causal connections between actions and outcomes, and contribute to organizational learning.

The notion of reflection is closely connected to sense making. Reflection is an integral part of sense making. The following description points out (1) an intricate nature of how we make our conclusions based on our understanding of apparent causal relationships, and (2) the role of reflection in going beyond the apparent and making sense of the situation (Weick & Sutcliffe, 2005; page 409-410):

"Sensemaking is about the interplay of action and interpretation rather than the influence of evaluation on choice. When action is the central focus, interpretation, not choice, is the core phenomenon (Laroche 1995, p. 66; Lant 2002; Weick 1993, pp. 644–646). Scott Snook (2001) makes this clear in his analysis of a friendly fire incident over Iraq in April 1994 when two F-15 pilots shot down two friendly helicopters, killing 26 people. As Snook says, this is not an incident where F-15 pilots "decided" to pull the trigger. I

could have asked, “Why did they decide to shoot?” However, such a framing puts us squarely on a path that leads straight back to the individual decision maker, away from potentially powerful contextual features and right back into the jaws of the fundamental attribution error. “Why did they decide to shoot?” quickly becomes “Why did they make the wrong decision?” Hence, the attribution falls squarely onto the shoulders of the decision maker and away from potent situation factors that influence action. Framing the individual-level puzzle as a question of meaning rather than deciding shifts the emphasis away from individual decision makers toward a point somewhere “out there” where context and individual action overlap... . Such a reframing—from decision making to sensemaking—opened my eyes to the possibility that, given the circumstances, even I could have made the same “dumb mistake.” This disturbing revelation, one that I was in no way looking for, underscores the importance of initially framing such senseless tragedies as “good people struggling to make sense,” rather than as “bad ones making poor decisions” (pp. 206–207).”

The above description also points out that the way we frame the situation (the way we make sense out of it) could influence both the learning content and the learning process, at least to a certain degree. Furthermore, this description emphasizes the relevance of considering knowledge as meaning, not merely as data – as we presented in our description of knowledge earlier.

5. Communicative processes – conversation/dialog

In order to share information, engage in collective reflection and sense making and hence learn in projects (as in the Rebuild project), it is essential to consider the role of communication and communicative relations between people who are involved in the projects. Conversation/dialog are some forms of communication between people. Dialog is "a sustained collective inquiry into the processes, assumptions, and certainties that compose everyday experience" (Issacs, 1993, page 25). In order to understand the significance of communicative processes, it is relevant to describe how we understand the reality.

We perceive and interpret the reality not necessarily in the same way. Figure 1 illustrates how our observation of something (for example, an event) is transformed into action (Senge et al., 1994)

Figure 1: Ladder of inference (Senge et al., 1994)

Difference in our understanding of the reality has implication for knowledge sharing and learning. We may have different opinion on what (and/or whether) we have learned in a given situation. Dialog/conversation between the involved parties can help to reduce or eliminate this difference and enhance an effective learning process. As Figure 1 presents, there are several steps of a process that we go through to understand the reality and take actions. These steps can be considered as concrete focal areas that we can focus on and find out

what we do (and can do) at these focal areas in order to create a common ground of understanding – which in turn can contribute to effective learning and knowledge sharing.

Meanings, assumptions, conclusions and beliefs that we develop are not always communicated adequately in cooperative work settings. A communicative process (conversation/dialog) – formal as well as informal – can help to reveal the underlying constructs of our understanding and actions. This, in turn, can provide us with a correct understanding of (1) for example, handling of a problematic situation, and (2) what (and/or whether) we have learned in a given situation; for instance, what has actually happened, *What* caused it (followed by the *why, how, who, when* and *where* questions), what is there to be learned / what knowledge that we gain here.

Now, we will briefly look at how communicative processes (conversation/dialog) can be compared with the categorization of knowledge (Spender, 2008) that we have presented earlier:

- Knowledge-as-data: Data and information, which are available in documents, can be used as a point of departure as well as a facilitating means for communicative processes.
- Knowledge-as-meaning: Individual and collective reflection and sense making can be seen as core aspects of conversation/dialog that is aimed at creating a common ground for understanding and learning. Shared space for emerging relationships (*Ba*) facilitates reflection and sense making and hence promotes meaning creation. (More on *Ba* will be presented in the following section.)
- Knowledge-as-practice: Conversation/dialog is a social process, and it can contribute to understand the *what, why, how, who, when* and *where* questions related to learning (what causes what, etc.). This understanding will ensure the right practice of the right knowledge.

6. Ba

A notion that can contribute notably to communicative processes (and also to deal effectively with collective reflection, sense making and learning in project settings), is *Ba*. The notion of *Ba* is described as "a shared space for emerging relationships" in which knowledge is embedded (Nonaka & Konno, 1998; page 40). This space can be physical (for example, office), virtual (for example, e-mail), mental (for example, shared experiences) or any combination of these three types of spaces. Socialization between the cooperating actors and their inter-connectedness improve exploitation and exploration of knowledge in organizations (Eriksson, 2013). *Ba* plays a significant role in the whole process of organizational knowledge creation (Nonaka & Konno, 1998). *Ba* can facilitate sharing and creating knowledge through the interplay between tacit and explicit knowledge – the interplay that takes place in processes such as socialization, externalization, combination and institutionalization (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995). Furthermore, the communicative relation that is emphasized in connection with the description of knowledge creation and learning (Stacey, 2001-a, 2001-b) can also be compared with the notion of *Ba*.

Existence and application of *Ba* were studied in several research studies; for instance, the development of Prius at the Motor Corporation (Faccin & Balestrin, 2018).

7. What do Rebuild primarily do for capturing learning in the project?

Rebuild has regular meetings with all of its partners – twice a year (in addition to more frequent online meetings). These meetings are arenas for collective reflection, sharing knowledge and experience, identifying challenges and opportunities. Dialog plays a central role in this regard.

These meetings generally include presentations – of what has been done so far in the project work, challenges (if any) that are to be dealt with – from each partner or the leader of the work-packages, followed by questions, discussions and clarifications. These presentations also provide information to other partners to understand the progression of the project both at the macro and micro level. At macro level, the partners can gain an understanding of how the project, as a whole, is progressing. At micro level, they will become to know how progression in one work-package can contribute to or influence their own work-packages. More understanding of the interconnection between the work-packages will eventually emerge, which can prompt to identifying new opportunities as well as challenges.

Information provided by the presentations in these meetings will lead to develop knowledge further. The connection between information and knowledge is important to mention here. When a new information emerges, existing knowledge contributes to interpret the new information. The understanding that is derived from interpreting the information represents and / or is included in the existing knowledge. The updated existing knowledge will again contribute to interpret and understand any new relevant information. This process is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: A connection between knowledge and information

Conversation/dialog in these meetings not only facilitates learning and knowledge sharing, but also strengthens a common ground of understanding, which is important for the future, collective learning process and for improving the project performance.

Several European countries are involved in Rezbuild. The demonstration projects where Rezbuild tests out sustainable solutions for refurbishment of existing building stocks are located in Italy, Spain, UK and Norway. Generally speaking, it is important to understand differences in the national context (national work culture, work practices, etc.). This understanding is helpful to avoid incorrect assumptions that project participants could have regarding each other's project contribution. Incorrect assumptions and misunderstanding can cause not only delay, extra cost and bad quality that is associated with a project delivery, but also a work climate that is not conducive to collaborative spirit, happiness in workplace, efficiency and effectiveness. Conversation/dialog can act as a mechanism for bringing the implicit assumptions to the surface and examine its validity, and thus contribute to create a common ground for understanding. This common ground is important for learning and knowledge sharing. The bi-annual meetings conducted in Rezbuild provide the partners an arena for dialog, where information is exchanged and reflected upon collectively to create a common ground for understanding, learn more about the project and then devise action-plan for the future.

Rezbuild conducts more frequent online meetings too. Face-to-face discussions and socialization in the bi-annual meetings can contribute to ensure productivity of the online meetings; for example, even though the partners do not have direct face-to-face contact online, there is less threshold to speak openly, supporting each other and knowledge sharing, because they met face-to-face before in the bi-annual meeting. The online meetings can contribute to follow up the action-plan that is devised in the bi-annual meetings and deal with the challenges that could emerge. It can also be said that the quality of dialog that was established in the bi-annual meetings is re-activated (or even improved) by the more frequent online meetings.

The central role of communicative relations in learning and development of knowledge that was mentioned earlier (Stacey, 2001-a, 2001-b) can be compared here with respect to bi-annual meetings and online meetings.

In addition, Rezbuild uses also a questionnaire to capture lessons learned in a six month period between project-partner-meetings. The questionnaire too provides possibilities for reflection and hence contributes to learning. It deals with, for instance, the following issues:

- The degree of understanding that is obtained regarding own and other work-packages, as well as the project as whole
- Skills that contributed to the project and the challenges of the project during the period
- Improvement possibilities
- Most interesting result for the project partner and the corresponding organization, obtained during the period
- Important lessons learned for the project partner and for the project during the period – along with an explanation of why it is important
- Changes in the organization and its role in the project due to the gained insight
- Perception of the likelihood of achieving the objectives of the work-package as well the project

Information obtained from the project partners will become a base for understanding the current nature of the situation and providing possibilities for improving performance of the project.

The meetings and questionnaire studies act as two major pillars for continuous learning in Rebuild.

7.1 Effects of continuous learning within a project

An effect of continuous learning within a project is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Continuous learning within a project

As Figure 3 shows, the positive effect of continuous learning can be viewed in two dimensions:

- Intra-project learning: This is about improving the project's productivity and performance. This improvement can be a result of single-loop learning (improvement by adhering to the norms) or double-loop learning (improvement by questioning the norms). Reflecting on results of actions (specifically, reflecting on the gap between the expected result and the actual result) will lead to these two types of learning. More on single-loop and double-loop learning can be referred in Argyris & Schön (1996). In the Rebuild project, dialog between the partners (who are from various European countries) plays a notable role in understanding what is to be learned in the project, so that the project's performance will be improved.
- Inter-project learning: This is about sharing lessons learned from project to project. In addition to its intra-project learning, Rebuild also looks at lessons learned from other similar projects. Inter-project learning also focuses on social aspects (that include communicative relations). "Learning between projects [...] is a social accomplishment taking place within projects and through goal-oriented activities that enact knowledge embedded in the interlinking project context." (Hartmann & Dorée, 2015; page 350). Duffield & Whitty (2016) also point out the people-related aspects (social and cultural aspects) in lessons learned situations in projects.

Learning acquired actively by combining these two dimensions can provide a solid base for developing a learning organization. A learning organization is likely to support continuous learning in its project(s).

6. Concluding remarks

Research projects are aimed at adding value to the society. Conducting research projects effectively, influences results of research projects. Thus, it is important to look at opportunities for improving project performance. Learning and knowledge sharing is an appropriate process to consider in this regard. In this process, it is vital to define what we have learned and what knowledge that we have actually gained. This paper aims to shed some light on certain vital aspects of making such definition.

In the midst of the complexity that prevails in organizations and work settings, the causal relationships (between actions and results) are not always linear / clear. In other words, it may not be always possible to easily identify: what causes what, how it causes, why it causes, when it causes, where it causes, who causes. This situation has implications for learning and for defining what knowledge that we have gained through the learning process.

Conversation/dialog can contribute to deal with the complexity that is associated with learning and knowledge sharing. They, when properly applied, can unveil among other things:

- Knowing how each cooperating actor perceives and interprets the reality
- Creating a common ground for understanding
- Identifying the underlying reasons for results and the dynamic that has triggered and shaped the formation of the results

Conversation/dialog can be carried out and facilitated effectively through creating *Ba*. *Ba* can help not only to address the complexity that is associated with learning, but also to contribute promote and enhance communicative relations that are, according to Stacey (2001-a, 2001-b), pivotal for learning and knowledge creation.

This paper presents a theoretical discussion on the above mentioned issue, as well as the learning processes that have been implemented in the Rebuild project to ensure continuous improvement in project performance. The theoretical discussion can be considered as an initial step (and a guiding theoretical framework) to study more on the role of *Ba* and communicative relations in dealing with complexity that is associated with learning in projects.

This paper does not provide any results from empirical studies. Further research includes studying the results from the learning processes (the meetings and the questionnaire studies) and finding out the effect of the learning processes on the project performance.

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